

Open and reproducible coding: Perspective of an MSK imaging researcher

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Find the presentation on Zenodo

tinyurl.com/baseltea

How I started coding in an open and
reproducible way...

I had to segment and analyze some knee images...

- Collaboration with scientists with limited experience in medical imaging

I had to segment and analyze some knee images...

- Collaboration with scientists with limited experience in medical imaging
- They ***needed code*** to extract measures of osteoarthritis progression

➔ First thing: Segmentation!

I looked for existing algorithms around...

Literature map of femoral knee cartilage segmentation

I looked for existing algorithms around...

Literature map of femoral knee cartilage segmentation

What to do?

- I was not interested to create another algorithm
 - There were already 29 around!
- I needed to create a **workflow** to segment and analyze knee images
 - Use of already existing algorithms
 - Focus on “putting the pieces together” and **ease of use**

Image from:
<https://dribbble.com/shots/964040-Blog-Illo-gif>

Somehow I started...

- Initially, I wanted to use Matlab
 - It was what I knew, and I already had some code
 - *But* it is not open source! Not everybody has a Matlab license
 - I did not want to write new closed source code (and be the 28th!)
- So I started in C++
 - I could use open libraries: ITK and elastix
 - *But* I had to create executables for Windows - I work in MacOS!
 - Command lines are not ideal for people with limited coding experience and coding in C++ is hard for me
 - Pipeline still fragmented (e.g. code vs. visualization)

But I was still looking for a better solution...

- A statistician showed me reproducible workflow using R markdown

The screenshot shows a browser window displaying an R Markdown document. The title is "R Markdown". The text explains that R Markdown is a simple formatting syntax for authoring HTML, PDF, and MS Word documents. It provides a link to <http://rmarkdown.rstudio.com>. Below this, it explains that clicking the "Knit" button generates a document including content and output of embedded R code chunks. An example R code chunk is shown: `summary(cars)`. The output of this code is displayed as a table of summary statistics for the 'cars' dataset. Below the table, it says "You can also embed plots, for example:" and shows a scatter plot of 'dist' (distance) versus 'speed' (miles per hour) from the 'cars' dataset.

```
summary(cars)
```

##	speed	dist
##	Min. : 4.0	Min. : 2
##	1st Qu.:12.0	1st Qu.: 26
##	Median :15.0	Median : 36
##	Mean :15.4	Mean : 43
##	3rd Qu.:19.0	3rd Qu.: 56
##	Max. :25.0	Max. :120

You can also embed plots, for example:

The scatter plot shows the relationship between speed (x-axis, 0 to 25) and distance (y-axis, 0 to 120). The data points show a positive correlation, with distance increasing as speed increases. The plot is a simple scatter plot with open circles for data points.

But I was still looking for a better solution...

- A statistician showed me reproducible workflow using R markdown
- There was something similar for Python, something new which was getting more and more popular...

Jupyter notebook!!!

The image displays three Jupyter notebook windows side-by-side, illustrating the use of Jupyter notebooks for different programming languages.

- Julia.ipynb:** Shows a plot of Sepal.Length vs Sepal.Width for the Iris dataset, with points colored by species. Below the plot, the output of `eigen(x)` is shown, displaying eigenvalues and eigenvectors.
- Lorenz.ipynb:** Shows the Lorenz system of differential equations: $\dot{x} = \sigma(y - x)$, $\dot{y} = \rho x - y - xz$, and $\dot{z} = -\beta z + xy$. It includes a slider for `sigma` and a plot of the Lorenz attractor.
- R.ipynb:** Shows a scatter plot of Sepal.Length vs Sepal.Width for the Iris dataset, with points colored by species. Below the plot, the output of `head(iris)` is shown, displaying the first few rows of the Iris dataset.

I created **PYKNEER** !

- An image analysis workflow for **open** and **reproducible** research on femoral knee cartilage

1. Preprocessing

2. Segmentation

3. Analysis

Morphology

Relaxometry

Structure of **pyKNEER**

- Each part has one (or two) Jupyter notebooks as a user-interface
 - From data upload to result visualization in one file
- “Behind” the notebooks there is the pyKNEER python package
 - Divided in modules
 - Contains core functions
- Users can load their images and run the notebook

pykneer_example_2.ipynb

Relaxometry - Extended Phase Graph (EPG) modeling

Image information

Inputs:

- `input_file_name` contains the list of the images used to calculate T_2 using EPG modeling
- `output_file_name` contains average and standard deviation of the T_2 maps

```
input_file_name = "./image_list_relaxometry_EPG.txt"
output_file_name = "EPG_demo.csv"
```

Read image data

- `image_data` is a dictionary (or struct), where each cell corresponds to an image. For each image, information such as paths and file names are stored

```
image_data = io.load_image_data_EPG(input_file_name)
01_DESS_01_orig
-> information loaded for 1 subjects
```

Calculate T_2 maps

```
rel.calculate_t2_maps(image_data, n_of_cores)
01_DESS_01_orig
-> T2 maps calculated
-> The total time was 2.54 seconds (about 0 min)
```

Visualize T_2 maps

2D MAP: For each image, fitting maps at medial and lateral compartments and flattened map
The flattened map is an average of neighboring voxels projected on the bone surface side of the femoral cartilage

```
rel.show_t2_maps(image_data)
```

3D MAP: Interactive rendering of T_2 maps

```
# ID of the map to visualize (The ID is the one in the 2D visualization above)
image_ID = 1 -1 -1 because counting starts from 0

# read image
file_name = image_data[image_ID]["relaxometryFolder"] + image_data[image_ID]["t2mapMaskFileName"]
image = itk.imread(file_name)

# view
viewer = view(image, gradient_opacity=0.0, ui_collapsed=False, shadow=False)
viewer
```

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Let's have a look!

How does the Jupyter/Python environment work?

The Jupyter/Python environment

The Jupyter/Python environment

The Jupyter/Python environment

The Jupyter/Python environment

Installation - Anaconda

- www.anaconda.com/products/distribution

The screenshot displays the Anaconda Navigator desktop application. The interface is divided into a left sidebar and a main content area. The sidebar contains navigation options: Environments, Learning, and Community. The main content area shows a grid of application cards for different tools, each with a description and a button to either 'Launch' or 'Install'.

Applications on base (root) Channels

Application	Version	Action
Datalore		Launch
IBM Watson Studio Cloud		Launch
JupyterLab	3.0.11	Launch
Jupyter Notebook	6.3.0	Launch
PyCharm Community	2019.1.3	Launch
Qt Console	5.0.3	Launch
Spyder	4.1.5	Launch
Glueviz	1.0.0	Install
Orange 3	3.26.0	Install
PyCharm Professional		Install
RStudio	1.1.456	Install

The interface also includes a top navigation bar with 'Upgrade Now' and 'Sign in' buttons, and a bottom sidebar with social media links for Twitter, YouTube, and GitHub.

JupyterLab

The screenshot shows the JupyterLab web interface in a browser window. The address bar (1) displays the URL `localhost:8888/lab/book/notebooks/`. The top navigation menu (2) includes File, Edit, View, Run, Kernel, Tabs, Settings, and Help. The left sidebar (3) contains a file browser with a search bar (4) and a file list (5) showing folders like Applications, data, Desktop, Documents, and Downloads, along with their last modified dates. The main area (7) is the Launcher, which offers options to create a Notebook (8) using Python 3, a Console, or other file types like Terminal, Text File, Markdown File, and Show Contextual Help. The status bar at the bottom shows 'Simple' mode, a file named '1', a terminal icon, '48', 'Saving completed', 'English (American)', and 'Launcher'.

JupyterLab

Jupyter Notebook

- Released in 2014 by Fernando Perez, as an evolution of IPython
- Web-based application supporting various programming languages
- Integrates narrative (text, images, equations), code, and visualizations

The image displays three side-by-side screenshots of Jupyter Notebook interfaces for different programming languages: Julia, Python, and R.

Julia.ipynb: Shows a scatter plot of Sepal.Length vs Sepal.Width for three species (setosa, versicolour, virginica). The code uses `using RDatasets, Gadfly` and `plot(dataset("datasets", "iris"), x="Sepal.Width", y="Sepal.Length", color=:Species)`. Below the plot, it shows the output of `eigen(x)`, displaying eigenvalues and eigenvectors.

Lorenz.ipynb: Shows a Python notebook with the title "python notebook". It includes a code cell for `from matplotlib inline` and `from ipywidgets import interactive, fixed`. The notebook contains a narrative about the Lorenz system of differential equations: $\dot{x} = \sigma(y - x)$, $\dot{y} = \rho x - y - xz$, and $\dot{z} = -\beta z + xy$. It also includes a code cell for `from lorenz import solve_lorenz` and an interactive widget for `w = interactive(solve_lorenz, sigma=(0.0, 50.0), rho=(10.0, 20.0), beta=(2.6666666666666666, 2.6666666666666666))`.

R.ipynb: Shows an R notebook with a scatter plot of Sepal.Length vs Sepal.Width. The code uses `ggplot(data=iris, aes(x=Sepal.Length, y=Sepal.Width))`. Below the plot, it shows the output of `head(iris)`, displaying the first few rows of the iris dataset.

Sepal.Length	Sepal.Width	Petal.Length
5.1	3.5	1.4
4.9	3.0	1.4

Jupyter Notebook

The screenshot displays the JupyterLab web interface. The browser address bar shows `localhost:8888/lab/tree/Dropbox/book/notebooks/practicing_cells.ipynb`. The interface includes a file browser on the left (1), a notebook editor window (2) with a toolbar (3) and code cells (5), and a status bar at the bottom (4) showing 'Python 3 | Idle' and 'Saving completed'.

Jupyter Notebook - Narrative

- Language: Markdown
 - [markdownguide.org](https://www.markdownguide.org)
- Text

Jupyter Notebook - Narrative

- Language: Markdown
 - [markdownguide.org](https://www.markdownguide.org)
- Text
- Equations

Jupyter Notebook - Narrative

- Language: Markdown
 - [markdownguide.org](https://www.markdownguide.org)

- Text
- Equations
- Images

Python

- Created by Guido van Rossum in 1991
- Data types

```
my_notebook.ipynb
+ ✂ 📄 ▶ ■ ↺ Code ▾

Introduction to Python in a Jupyter notebook

Data types

Strings

[1]: a = "This is a string"
    print (a)
This is a string

Lists (=arrays)

[2]: b = [1,2,3]
    print (b)
[1, 2, 3]

Tuples (=immutable lists)

[3]: c = (1,2,3)
    print (c)
(1, 2, 3)

Booleans

[8]: d = True
    print (d)
True

[9]: e = False
    print (e)
False

Dictionaries

[11]: f = {'first': 1,
         'second': [0,1,2]}
      print (f)
{'first': 1, 'second': [0, 1, 2]}
```


Python

- Created by Guido van Rossum in 1991
- Data types
- Conditions and loops

```
my_notebook.ipynb x
+ ✂ 📄 📄 ▶ ⏪ ⏩ Code ▾

Conditional statements

[1]: 1 a = 5
      2 b = 10
      3
      4 if b > a:
      5     print("b is greater than a")
      6 elif a == b:
      7     print("a and b are equal")
      8 else:
      9     print("a is greater than b")

b is greater than a

For loops

[2]: 1 # for loop through indices
      2 for x in range(2, 5): # Note: [start, stop)
      3     print(x)

2
3
4

[3]: 1 # for loop through values
      2 numbers = [2,3,4]
      3 for number in numbers:
      4     print(number)

2
3
4

While loop

[4]: 1 answer = input("Do you like coding?")
      2
      3 while answer == "yes":
      4
      5     print("Yeah!")
      6     answer = input("Do you like coding?")
      7
      8 print("whaaaatttt?!?!")

Do you like coding? yes
Yeah!
Do you like coding? yes
Yeah!
Do you like coding? no
whaaaatttt?!?!?
```


Python

- Created by Guido van Rossum in 1991
- Data types
- Conditions and loops
- Functions

```
my_notebook.ipynb
+ ✂ 📄 ▶ ■ ↺ ⏪ Markdown
Functions
Basic syntax:
[15]: 1 def print_favorite_food():
      2
      3     my_taste = "my favorite food"
      4
      5     print (my_taste)
[16]: 1 print_favorite_food()
      my favorite food
Provide input:
[17]: 1 def print_favorite_food(my_favorite_food):
      2
      3     my_taste = "my favorite food is: " + my_favorite_food
      4
      5     print (my_taste)
[18]: 1 print_favorite_food("gorgonzola cheese")
      my favorite food is: gorgonzola cheese
Provide input and return output:
[19]: 1 def print_favorite_food(my_favorite_food):
      2
      3     my_taste = "my favorite food is: " + my_favorite_food
      4
      5     return my_taste
[20]: 1 my_fav_food = print_favorite_food("gorgonzola cheese")
      2 print (my_fav_food)
      my favorite food is: gorgonzola cheese
```


Python

- Created by Guido van Rossum in 1991
- Data types
- Conditions and loops
- Functions
- Simple syntax
- Readable

```
my_notebook.ipynb
+ ✂ 📄 ▶ ■ ↺ ▶▶ Markdown
Functions
Basic syntax:
[15]: 1 def print_favorite_food():
      2
      3     my_taste = "my favorite food"
      4
      5     print (my_taste)
[16]: 1 print_favorite_food()
      my favorite food
Provide input:
[17]: 1 def print_favorite_food(my_favorite_food):
      2
      3     my_taste = "my favorite food is: " + my_favorite_food
      4
      5     print (my_taste)
[18]: 1 print_favorite_food("gorgonzola cheese")
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Provide input and return output:
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      4
      5     return my_taste
[20]: 1 my_fav_food = print_favorite_food("gorgonzola cheese")
      2 print (my_fav_food)
      my favorite food is: gorgonzola cheese
```


Python packages

- On PyPI there are more than 400K projects

`pip install`

The screenshot shows the PyPI website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Help, Sponsors, Log in, and Register. The main heading reads "Find, install and publish Python packages with the Python Package Index". Below this is a search bar labeled "Search projects" and a link to "Or browse projects". A statistics bar displays: 414,250 projects, 3,926,980 releases, 7,035,029 files, and 637,798 users. The footer contains the Python Package Index logo and a description: "The Python Package Index (PyPI) is a repository of software for the Python programming language. PyPI helps you find and install software developed and shared by the Python community. [Learn about installing packages](#). Package authors use PyPI to distribute their software. [Learn how to package your Python code for PyPI](#)."

Python packages

- On PyPI there are more than 400K projects
- NumFOCUS sponsored projects
- Packages for specific research fields

NUMFOCUS
OPEN CODE = BETTER SCIENCE

What else is in Jupyter/Python?

- Binder
mybinder.org

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=owSGVOov9pQ>

What else is in Jupyter/Python?

- Binder
mybinder.org
- Jupyter book
jupyterbook.org

The screenshot shows the Jupyter Book website homepage. The header includes the 'jupyter {book}' logo, a search bar, and navigation icons. The main content area features a large heading: 'Build beautiful, publication-quality books and documents from computational content.' Below this is a 'Get started' button and a badge showing 'Stars 3.1k' and 'DOI 10.5281/zenodo.2561065'. The 'JB' logo is prominently displayed on the right. A sidebar on the left contains a table of contents with sections for TUTORIALS, TOPIC GUIDES, and REFERENCE. The main content area is divided into six cards: Text content, MyST Markdown, Executable content, Live environments, Build and publish, and UI components.

jupyter {book}

Search this book...

TUTORIALS

- Create your first book
- Get started with references

TOPIC GUIDES

- Structure and organize content
- Write narrative content
- Write executable content
- Build and publish outputs
- Web and internet features
- Sphinx usage and customization
- Advanced Jupyter Book Usage
- Contribute to Jupyter Book

REFERENCE

- Configuration reference
- MyST syntax cheat sheet
- Command-line interface reference
- Glossary

Read the Docs v: stable

Build beautiful, publication-quality books and documents from computational content.

Get started

Stars 3.1k DOI 10.5281/zenodo.2561065

JB

Text content

Structure books with text files and Jupyter Notebooks with minimal configuration.

MyST Markdown

Write MyST Markdown to create enriched documents with publication-quality features.

Executable content

Execute notebook cells, store results, and insert outputs across pages.

Live environments

Connect your book with Binder, JupyterHub, and other live environments

Build and publish

Share your built books via web services and hosted websites.

UI components

Create interactive and web-native components and services.

Contents

- Built with Jupyter Book
- Connect with us
- Acknowledgements

What else is in Jupyter/Python?

- Binder
mybinder.org
- Jupyter book
jupyterbook.org
- Jupyter Hub
jupyter.org/hub

The screenshot shows the JupyterHub website homepage. At the top left is the Jupyter logo and the word "jupyter". To the right is a navigation menu with links: "Try", "Install", "Get Involved", "Documentation", "News", "Governance", "Security", and "About". The main content area features the JupyterHub logo, which consists of the word "jupyterhub" in a sans-serif font, with an orange circular graphic element behind it. Below the logo is the text: "A multi-user version of the notebook designed for companies, classrooms and research labs". Further down, there is a section titled "What is JupyterHub?" followed by a paragraph of text: "JupyterHub brings the power of notebooks to groups of users. It gives users access to computational environments and resources without burdening the users with installation and maintenance tasks. Users - including students, researchers, and data scientists - can get their work done in their own workspaces on shared resources which can be managed efficiently by system administrators."

What else is in Jupyter/Python?

- Binder

mybinder.org

- Jupyter book

jupyterbook.org

- Jupyter Hub

jupyter.org/hub

- Wonderful, inspirational people

- Follow them on Twitter (Mastodon?) and watch their talks on YouTube!

Fernando
Perez

Chris
Holdgraf

Lorena
Barba

Damian Avila
UMSI & 2i2c
GitHub

Matthias
Bussonnier
QuanSight
GitHub

Sylvain Corlay
QuantStack
GitHub

Afshin Darian
Two Sigma
GitHub

Brian Granger
Amazon Web
Services
GitHub

Jason Grout
Databricks
GitHub

Jessica Hamrick
DeepMind
GitHub

Paul Ivanov
Noteable
GitHub

Thomas Kluyver
University of
Southampton
GitHub

Kyle Kelley
Noteable
GitHub

<https://jupyter.org/about>

Where to start?

How to transition to Jupyter/Python?

- Translate some existing code

How to transition to Jupyter/Python?

- Translate some existing code
- Plenty of online material
 - geeksforgeeks.org, medium.com for examples and theory
 - stackoverflow.com for bugs and questions
 - youtube.com videos

How to transition to Jupyter/Python?

- Translate some existing code
- Plenty of online material
 - [geeksforgeeks.org](https://www.geeksforgeeks.org), medium.com for examples and theory
 - stackoverflow.com for bugs and questions
 - [youtube.com](https://www.youtube.com) videos
- My contributions
 - Learn Python with Jupyter ([learnpythonwithjupyter.com](https://www.learnpythonwithjupyter.com))
 - Introduction to Jupyter notebook and Python ([youtube.com/playlist?list=PLj8QFvBykB7fGEH274TlqhToqGd_Qxt1H](https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLj8QFvBykB7fGEH274TlqhToqGd_Qxt1H))

How do we use
the Jupyter/Python environment
to create
open and reproducible code?

Structure of a *readable* Jupyter Notebook

- Organize the narrative:
 - Title, authors, licenses
 - Aim(s) + table of contents
 - Divide in paragraphs with subtitles
 - Introduce code
 - Comment the results
- Organize the code:
 - Package imports
 - Functions
 - Variables
 - Workflow body
 - Dependencies

Structure of a *reproducible* Jupyter Notebook

- Automatically download data from a repository
- Avoid manual intervention for data analysis
- Use seeds for randomness
- Dependencies, i.e., versions of libraries and machine

```
import wget

# file name
file_name = "cart_segmliterature.csv"

# zenodo url (3553483 are the last digits in Zenodo's DOI)
zenodo_url = "https://zenodo.org/record/3553483/files/"

# download (input, output)
wget.download(zenodo_url + file_name, "." + file_name)
```



```
np.random.seed(0)
```

```
%load_ext watermark
%watermark
%watermark --iversions
```

```
Last updated: 2022-05-06T19:26:43.755812+02:00

Python implementation: CPython
Python version       : 3.9.7
IPython version      : 7.29.0

Compiler   : Clang 10.0.0
OS         : Darwin
Release    : 21.1.0
Machine    : x86_64
Processor  : i386
CPU cores  : 8
Architecture: 64bit

sklearn: 0.24.2
scipy    : 1.7.1
numpy    : 1.20.3
```


youtube.com/watch?v=-9qSUJTuec8

github.com/rasbt/watermark

Best practices for open and reproducible computational research

- Write code and documentation for **human beings!**
 - Write **narrative** in Jupyter notebooks!
 - Write **code documentation!**
 - Style guide for Python Code (<https://peps.python.org/pep-0008/>)
 - Numpy style guide (<https://numpydoc.readthedocs.io/en/latest/format.html>)

```
def read_image(filename, format="SimpleITK"):
    """Reads an image from file as either a SimpleITK or ITK image. The default is SimpleITK

    Parameters
    -----
    filename : str
        Filename of the image to read (extension can be .mha, .mhd, etc.)
    format : str
        Format of the read image, defined by the user. It can be:
        - "SimpleITK": Reads the image using SimpleITK. It's the default
        - "ITK": Reads the image using ITK

    Returns
    -----
    img: SimpleITK or ITK
        Image in SimpleITK or ITK format
    """
```

docstring

sphinx
pdoc
pdoc3
doxygen

```
def read_image(filename, format='SimpleITK')
    Reads an image from file as either a SimpleITK or ITK image. The default is SimpleITK

    Parameters
    filename : str
        Filename of the image to read (extension can be .mha, .mhd, etc.)

    format : str
        Format of the read image, defined by the user. It can be: - "SimpleITK": Reads the image using SimpleITK.
        It's the default - "ITK": Reads the image using ITK

    Returns
    img : SimpleITK or ITK
        Image in SimpleITK or ITK format
```

HTML documentation

Best practices for open and reproducible computational research

- Write code and documentation for human beings!
- Work using version control tools

Best practices for open and reproducible computational research

- Write code and documentation for human beings!
- Work using version control tools
- Release code with an open-source license
 - choosealicense.com/licenses
 - Morin et al, 2012, *A Quick Guide to Software Licensing for the Scientist-Programmer* (doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1002598)
 - Video (youtube.com/watch?v=GIAnKGBnhFY)

Best practices for open and reproducible computational research

- Write code and documentation for human beings!
- Work using version control tools
- Release code with an open-source license
- In publications provide information about code and attach notebooks

	Repository	Metadata / Documentation	Software / Language	License	DOI	Citation
Software Used						
Preprocessing	Bitbucket	Wiki	C++, ITK	Apache	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2014.05.008 *	[59]*
elastix 4.8	GitHub	Github Wiki	C++, ITK	Apache	https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2009.2035616 *	[28]*
Developed pyKNEEr	GitHub	Website	python, Jupyter notebook	GNU GPLv3	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2574172	Bonaretti S. et al. "pyKNEER" (v0.0.1). Zenodo. 2019. 10.5281/zenodo.2574172
Data Original	OAI	Website	-	Data user agreement	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joca.2008.06.016 *	[49]*
Derived (results)	Zenodo	Jupyter notebook	-	CC-BY-NC-SA	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2530609	Bonaretti S. et al. Dataset used in (Bonaretti et al. 2019). Zenodo. 2019. 10.5281/zenodo.2530609

Best practices for open and reproducible computational research

- Write code and documentation for human beings!
- Work using version control tools
- Release code with an open-source license
- In publications provide information about code and attach notebooks

Dataset	OAI1-DESS	OAI1-T2	OAI2-BL	OAI2-FU	inHouse-DESS	inHouse-CQ
Number of subjects	19	19	88	88	4	4
I. Acquisition parameters						
Acquisition protocol	DESS	T ₂ -w	DESS	DESS	DESS	CubeQuant
Acquisition plane	sagittal	sagittal	sagittal	sagittal	sagittal	sagittal
Number of images in series	2 (1 available)*	7	2 (1 available)*	2	2	1
In-plane spacing [mm]	0.3646 x 0.3646 (0.4270 x 0.4270)*	0.3125 x 0.3125 (0.4296 x 0.4296)*	0.3646 x 0.3646	0.3125 x 0.3125	0.3125 x 0.3125	0.3125 x 0.3125
Slice thickness [mm]	0.7 (0.75)*	3 (3.5)*	0.7	1.5	3	-
Echo time (TE) [ms]	4.7	10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70	4.7	42.52	-	-
Spin-lock time (TSL) [ms]	-	-	-	-	1, 10, 30, 60	-
Repetition time (TR) [ms]	16.32	2700 (2900)*	16.32	25	1302	-
Flip angle [°]	25	180	25	30	90	-
II. Ground truth segmentation						
Method	atlas-based		active models		-	-
Anatomy	femur, femoral cartilage		femoral cartilage		-	-
Type	mask		contour		-	-
III. Experimental results						
Image number in series	1	1	2-7	1	1	2
Preprocessing						
Spatial standardization	•	•	•	•	•	•
Intensity standardization	•	•	•	•	•	•
Segmentation						
Find reference	4, 8, 10, 13, 16	-	-	-	-	-
Intersubject	-	-	-	-	-	-
Longitudinal	-	-	-	-	-	-
Multimodal	-	-	-	-	-	-
Segmentation quality						
Dice coefficient	•	•	•	•	•	•
Analysis						
Morphology	•	•	•	•	•	•
Relaxation	-	•	-	-	•	•

```

pyKNEER
Segmenting MR Knee Images

Import packages
from pykneeer import pykneeer, io
from pykneeer import segmentation, io_for, io, ioqa

Variables
input_file_name = "image_list_researcher.txt"
model_dir = "models"
n_of_cores = 1

Read image data
image_data = io.load_image_data(segmentation_model_dir, input_file_name)

Reference image
segm_prepare_reference(image_data)

Segment bone
Register image to reference, invert transformation, and warp reference mask to moving image
segm_register_bone_to_reference(image_data, n_of_cores)
segm_invert_bone_to_reference(image_data, n_of_cores)
segm_warp_bone_mask(image_data, n_of_cores)

Segment cartilage
Register image to reference, invert transformation, and warp reference mask to moving image
segm_register_cartilage_to_reference(image_data, n_of_cores)
segm_invert_cartilage_to_reference(image_data, n_of_cores)
segm_warp_cartilage_mask(image_data, n_of_cores)

Visualize segmentations
view_model = 0; # 0 for static, 1 for interactive
fig = ioqa.show_segmented_images(image_data, view_model)
display(fig)

Figure
01 DESS 01 prep - Slice 24    01 DESS 01 prep - Slice 15    01 DESS 01 prep - Slice 46
    
```


Figure 4: Results for the datasets OAI1-DESS (red), OAI1-T2 (green), OAI2-BL (cyan) and OAI2-FU (purple). (a) Violin plots describing the distribution of the DSC within each dataset. The dots represent DSC values spread around the y-axis to avoid visualization overlap. (b-d) Correlation between measurements of ground truth (x-axis) and pyKNEER (y-axis) of ground truth segmentations and pyKNEER's segmentations, i.e. cartilage thickness (b), cartilage volume (c), and T₂ maps (d).

Best practices for open and reproducible computational research

- Write code and documentation for human beings!
- Work using version control tools
- Release code with an open-source license
- In publications provide information about code and attach notebooks
- Get a DOI by connecting GitHub repository with Zenodo
 - GitHub documentation (<https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/archiving-a-github-repository/referencing-and-citing-content>)
 - Video ([youtube.com/watch?v=gp3D4mf6MHQ](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gp3D4mf6MHQ))

Some literature on best practices

- Ten simple rules for writing and sharing computational analyses in Jupyter Notebooks
(Rule et al, doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007007)
- Ten simple rules for reproducible computational research
(Sandve et al, doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003285)
- Ten simple rules for taking advantage of Git and GitHub
(Perez-Riverol et al, doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1004947)
- Good enough practices in scientific computing
(Wilson et al, doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1005510)
- A Quick Guide to Software Licensing for the Scientist-Programmer
(Morin et al, 2012, doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1002598)
- Toward the Geoscience paper of the future: Best practices for documenting and sharing research from data to software to provenance
(Gil et al, doi.org/10.1002/2015EA000136)

Is open and reproducible research
(coding) an individual effort?

NO! It's a **community** game!

What can we do?

We can join or organize ourselves
in communities!

Open and Reproducible Musculoskeletal Imaging Research (ORMIR) Community

Open and reproducible *computational*
research is not an ideology,
it's a concrete way of working

Nowadays, we have all the tools to do it

Let's do it!!!